

The Role of the Church in Curbing Domestic Violence Among Nigerian Christians for National Integration

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Abstract

The nation Nigeria is currently undergoing a lot of security challenges. Terrorism has continued to manifest in the shades of banditry, kidnapping, herdsman attack, suicide bombing and Boko Haram. Amidst these security challenges leading to bloodshed, violence and loss of lives and properties in Nigeria, it has also increased in domestic violence. From the findings in the course of this work, it is discovered that domestic violence is one of the evil vices in Nigerian society. The international, national and local media are replete with records and accounts of domestic violence every day. If the news is not about a husband killing a wife, then it may be a father violating his daughter. Furthermore, Nigeria women are beaten, raped and even murdered by members of their own family to a supposed transgression, ranging from delay in preparation of meals or visiting members of the family without their husbands' permission. Finally, in addition to the above findings, domestic violence poses threat to peaceful co-existence and harmonious living. It has the capacity to invariably affect all social groups in the society. More surprisingly is the spate at which this evil act is becoming rampant in the church of God in recent time. Hence, the paper seeks to unearth the role which the church can play in curbing domestic violence among Nigerian Christians for National integration. The paper recommends among others, that the leadership of the church should organize seminars and outreach programs where clergy men as well as professional counselors are invited to enlighten people especially on the need for curbing domestic violence for National integration. The study used socio-historical analytical approach and data were collected from articles, journals, textbooks and internet.

Keywords: Church, Domestic, Insecurity.

Introduction

Domestic Violence is one of the social vices that affects mankind in Nigeria today. The rate at which domestic violence is prevalent in Nigerian society, is worrisome. In Nigeria, there is no day that reported cases of this evil act has not been mentioned in the National dailies. Omale, attests to the above that if the news is not about the growing trend of "baby factories" dotting the nooks and crannies in Nigeria, it may be about a husband killing the wife or a wife killing the husband. He also notes that sometimes, it may be about the father violating his daughter sexually. According to the writer, Nigerian women are beaten, raped and murdered by members of their own family for supposed transgression, which can range from not having meals ready on time to visiting family members without their husband's permission. He concluded that some women even experience acid attacks from their husbands or boyfriends which cause extreme pain and disfigurement, sometimes leading to death of the victims.¹

Kunhiyop is also of the view with the above writer that many of us have experienced domestic violence, probably witnessed a mother, aunt, or a neighbour's wife or child being physically, verbally or psychologically abused.² Ushe, added to the above as he opined that in Nigerian society for instance, researches carried out by scholars shows a high percentage of abuse by male counterparts. According to him, women are regarded as second class or subordinate group who in most cases are dehumanized and socially abused by men. The subjugation of women in most parts of the world is based on social, economic and political status and the roles performed by women in the society.³ Bella in Abalaka affirmed that in view of the above assertion, women are weaker gender by nature and as such cannot be equated with men. He added that the philosophy of reducing the status of women to subordinate group makes their actions seemingly innocuous and psychologically dehumanized them. He

concluded that the denial of women rights and participation in the development of the society has both economic and political implications on larger society, and Nigeria is not an exception.⁴

Church

The word Church comes from a Greek word *ekklesia* meaning “an assembly.” It comes from the word *kaleo* meaning “accompany” (LK 9:11) while *ek* implies “out of,” that is, “an assembly of the called ones.” That is where we got the chosen ones in the New Testament or the elect.⁵ The above writer also notes that the word Church has three implications. First and foremost, it means the people of God throughout the ages, that is, from the beginning of creation to date that included the existed people before the creation of the Jews. Secondly, it also implies in a narrow sense a visible gathered people. He concluded that in a more restricted sense it means believers in Christ according to 1 Corinthians 10:32, Galatians 1:13.

The word which Jesus used and has been translated “church” meant originally a collection of people meeting, gathering or a community. It was the word used for the Old Testament community of Israel and was particularly suitable for the new community, the Christian and that came into being on the day of Pentecost (Exo. 12:13, 6:35, Deut. 9:10, 23:3, Matt. 18:18, Acts 5:11, 7:38, 8:1-11, 26).⁶ When one is speaking of the Church, there are at least polarities which must be kept in mind. First the church is both the whole body of Christ, (Catholic, Protestant, Anglican, Orthodox and Oriental) and a particular denomination or community within it. Secondly, the Church is both the whole body of God (Laity, religious and clergy alike) and particularly groups within it (e. g. the hierarchy or the official Church). Thirdly, the Church is both the universal and local Church. Indeed, the universal Church is the collection of local Churches.⁷

As the head has absolute control over the body, so Christ has supreme authority over the Church (Eph. 1:22-23). On the other hand, as the body shares in the life of the head so the Church shares in the life of the risen Christ. It is united in him in his victory over death and all the evil spiritual forces of the universe (Matt. 18:18, Eph. 1:21, 2:5-7, 3:10-21). In view of the above, Flemming, equally notes that if the picture of the body emphasizes the life, unity and growth that Christ gives to the Church, the picture of marriage emphasizes the love that Christ has for the Church. That love was so great that to gain the Church as his bride, Christ laid his life in sacrifice (Eph. 5:25, Acts 20:28).⁸ Flemming, further opined that the view of the Church in all its perfection as the body of Christ, is one that only God sees. According to him, man sees the Church in a world of sin and failure, (1 Cor. 3:1-3). God sees the Church as the total number of believers in all nations in all eras- a vast, ongoing, international community commonly referred to as the Church universally. While some sees it only in the form of those believers who are living in a particular place at a particular time.

The church is defined as the prophetic appearance of the kingdom. Two ideas flow from the definition: (i) the church is related to the kingdom; (ii) but the church is not equal to the kingdom of God. The historical Jesus founded or organize the church. Not until after the resurrection does the New Testament speak with regularity about the church. However, there are adumbration of the church in the teaching and ministry of Jesus, in both general and specific ways. In general, Jesus anticipated the later official formation of the church in that he gathered to himself twelve disciples, who constituted to the beginning of eschatological Israel, in effect the remnant. More specifically, Jesus explicitly referred to the church in two passages: Matt. 16-18-19 and 18:17. In the first passage, Jesus promised that he would build his church despite satanic opposition, thus assuring the ultimate success of His mission. The notion of the Church overcoming the forces of evil coincides with the idea that the Kingdom of God will prevail over its enemies. The second passage relate to the future organization of the Church, particularly its method of discipline, not unlike the Jewish synagogue practices of Jesus day.⁹

The New Testament identifies the church as the people of the Kingdom (Rev.5:10; etc.), not the kingdom itself. Moreover, the church is instrument of the kingdom. This is especially clear from Mathew 16:18-19, where the preaching of Peter and the church become the keys to opening up the kingdom to all who would enter. From the foregoing, we could speak of the church as a timeless and universal community, more commonly it speaks of it as a group of Christians meeting together in a particular locality.

Insecurity

The word “insecurity” has myriads of connotations. It signifies danger; hazard; uncertainty; lack of protection, and lack of safety. Beland in Ndubusi, O.P and Anigbuogu, T. defines insecurity as “the state of fear or anxiety stemming from a concrete or alleged lack of protection.” This according to them implies that insecurity is an absence of peace, order and security. The above writers equally note that insecurity can be defined from two perspectives. Firstly, insecurity is the state of being open or subject to danger or threat of danger where danger is the condition of being susceptible to harm or injury. Secondly, insecurity is the state of being exposed to risk or anxiety, where anxiety is a vague unpleasant emotion that is experienced in anticipation of some misfortune. These definitions of insecurity underscore a major point that those affected by insecurity are not only uncertain or unaware of what would happen but they are also vulnerable to the threats and dangers when they occur.

Domestic

Domestic simply means anything relating to the running of a home or to family relation, or for use in the home rather than in an industrial or office environment. It is mainly home-based activities.¹¹ The researcher attests to the above as he notes that activities normally associated with the home following occurrences of such activities are called domestic.

Forms of domestic violence

There are several forms or categories of domestic violence, each of which has its own devastating consequences. The various forms or types of violence can include physical abuse, sexual abuse, child-labour, spiritual as well as emotional.

(i) Physical Violence

This is the use of physical force in a way that it injures the victim or put him/her at the risk of being injured. It includes beating, kicking, knocking, punching, choking, confinement, among others. The physical abuse or battering form of violence is one of the commonest forms of abuse in the home.¹² Apart from abuse of power in intimate relationship within household, physical abuse can be linked to control and manipulation of the victim by the perpetrator.

(ii) Sexual abuse

This includes all forms of sexual assaults, harassment or exploitation. It involves forcing a person to participate in sexual activity, using a child for sexual purposes including child prostitution and pornography. Marital rape also come under this.

(iii) Child-labour

Child-labour takes the form of street vending, shop, market, beggars, guides for disabled beggars, head loaders in the markets, “wheelbarrow boys”, bus conductors among others. All these violate the right of the child education and good welfare. All over the country, many children are used for child-labour. In some cases, a whole family is dependent on the money these children bring home daily. Child-labour offence is a serious crime on paper because one has never heard of parents being arrested because his/her children are hawking on the streets.¹³

(iv) Spiritual abuse

This includes preventing a person from engaging in his/her spiritual or religious practices using one’s religious belief to manipulate, dominate or control him/her.

(v) Emotional abuse

This violence according to Fareo, has to do with threatening of a person, harming a person's sense of self-worth by putting him/her at risk of serious behavioural, cognitive, emotional as well as mental disorders. Furthermore, included in emotional abuse are name-calling, criticism, social isolation, intimidating or exploitative tendency, making unreasonable demand, terrorizing a person verbally or physically and exposing a child to violence.¹⁴

Causes of domestic violence

There are several causes of domestic violence notably among them are:

(i) Family upbringing

An individual's upbringing and moral values play major role in the way that a person treat others, especially the family members. Often, abusive parents grew up in homes where their parents were emotionally uninvolved, physically absent, abusive, involved in substance abuse or caught up in the world of success (devoting more time to work and business meetings than the welfare of the home). This issue may be one of the least reasons for domestic violence, but it seems to be very foundational to the various causes of domestic violence. A man who grew up in the family where the father does not respect the mother or grew up to believe that one can beat the wife because that was the way the father always did to the mother will equally do the same to his own wife; it is hard for such a child not to become a wife beater when he eventually gets married at the later stage of his life. It is sad and so unfortunate that some husbands beat their wives openly in the presence of their children. In regard to this Ishiola has this to say: "Some men even bring their sex partners and concubines to their matrimonial homes and the wife dare not say a word, and sadly their children are watching all of these. Such children will grow up and do worse than their father unless God takes control of their lives."¹⁵ There is a popular adage according to the above writers that goes "whatever a snake begets it must have a long tail". Children tend to copy whatever they see their parents do, for such children nothing is judged to be wrong as long as their parents does it.

(ii) Denial of sex

Because the woman is often assumed to be man's property, he assumes that he has a right to have sex with her any time he wishes. Should the wife show any resistance or unwillingness, she may be verbally abused or beaten.¹⁶The researcher lays credence to the above a she asserts that the view of Kunhiyop, may be correct because a village (Ofaji) in Igalaland of Kogi State, couple were seen exchanging words which resulted to beating, kicking, knocking, punching over persistent refusal of the wife for denial of sex as such became a disgrace to the family and the society at large.

(iii) Social Learning

If one observes a violent behaviour, one is more likely to imitate it. According to Crowell and Sugarman, if there are no negative consequences and the victim also accepts the violence with sub mission, then the behaviour will likely continue. They added that often violence is transmitted from generation to generation in cyclical manner.¹⁷

(iv) Social stress

Stress may be increased when a person is living in a family situation, with increased pressures. Violence according to Seltzer and Kalmus, is not always caused by stress, but may be one of the ways that some people response to stress.¹⁸ Jewkes, added that couples in poverty may be more likely to experience domestic violence, due to increased stress and conflicts about finances and other aspects.¹⁹

(v) Alcohol abuse

Some men abuse alcohol and other drugs. In their drunken state, they are unable to tolerate any disagreement from their spouses or children and are liable to interpret any action as insulting or insubordinate, and they respond to this with violence.²⁰

(vi) Jealousy

Many cases of domestic violence against women occur due to jealousy when the spouse either suspected of being unfaithful or planning to leave the relationship. An evolutionary psychology explanation of such cases of domestic violence against women is that they represent to male attempts to control female reproduction and ensure sexual exclusivity for himself through violence or threat of violence.²¹ Kunhiyop, added to the above that some men are so jealous and possessive that they do not even want to see their wife even taken to another man. According to him, any exchange with a man, no matter how innocent will result in a confrontation. He concluded that if the wife's responses are judged unsatisfactory, she will be battered.²²

(vii) Childlessness

One of the several reasons for domestic violence is childlessness. According to Omale, the reason why a woman might be treated is because of her inability to bear children, which culturally is seen as a fault from the woman rather than the man, whereas the problem may be from both of them. The woman takes the whole blame for the childlessness of the couple. Any woman who has not been able to bear children is seen as an enemy of progress and so she deserves to be treated harshly. In most cases, both her husband and in-law can ridicule, abuse, and even beat her at will. He concluded that a lot of women had to contend with serious rivalry because the man is permitted by tradition to take another wife who will bear him children. She could be subjected to violence for not preparing meals on time, having or being under suspicion of having sexual relationship outside the marriage.²³

(viii) Financial Issue

As one of the several causes of domestic violence, the man according to Omale, is considered the bread winner of the home, the Nigeria society is no different. He is expected to make money available for the family upkeep. However, these days it has become expedient for the woman to take on some kind of job either to fulfill her professional goal or to supplement the family food budget. When this is not forthcoming, is the beginning of danger signal especially if the woman can afford to make a substantial contribution. The danger becomes even more acute if the woman believes the man makes more money but fails to give sufficient amount to feed the family. The woman nags and complains in the presence of the children. She makes the children feel that their father has failed in his duty and therefore, he is useless and irresponsible. He concluded that quarrels usually ensue; even fighting, swearing and cursing becomes the order of the day. Obviously, a poor emotional environment is created. The couple may now be co-habiting and not really be living a happy family. In a nutshell, love is lost, and respect is lost for one another. At this point anything is possible.²⁴ Finally, physical and emotional weakness also serves as one of the causes of domestic violence. Men are regarded as physically strong while women are characterized as passive, dependent and physically and emotionally weak. This characterization makes it difficult for women to resist abuse.²⁵

Effects of Domestic Violence

Domestic violence has adverse effects on its victims who leave in a climate of fear and intimidation.

(i) Effects on Children

There has been an increase in acknowledgement that a child who is exposed to domestic violence during his upbringing will suffer in the development and psychological welfare. Some emotional and behavioural problems that can result due to domestic violence include increased aggressiveness, anxiety, and changes in how a child socializes friends, family and authorities. Problems with attitude and cognition in schools can start developing, along with a lack of skills such as problem-solving. Correlation has been found between the experience of the abuse and neglect in childhood and perpetrating domestic violence and sexual abuse in adulthood.²⁶ The abuser will purposely abuse the mother in front of the child to cause a ripple effect, hurting two victims simultaneously. He concluded that children who witness mother-assault are more likely to exhibit symptoms of posttraumatic stress disorder.²⁷ In view of the above, Kunyihop, equally notes that when a wife flees a violent marriage, she may have to leave her children behind, to be raised without the loving care of

their mother. If she is allowed to take the female children with her, they will grow up without a father. But even if the mother stays and endures the violence, the children will be scared by the home environment. He further asserts that children learn from what they see happening around them. He concluded that they will learn violence as they watch their fathers beat and molest their mothers. Children who have been abused often become delinquent and abusive in their relationships with other children.²⁸

(ii) Physical Effects

Physical impacts have to do with injuries which can lead to permanent disabilities in women or even leads to death of a woman. Sometimes, physical violence on a woman can lead to miscarriage of forced abortion and unwanted pregnancies. Some victims of violence often time than not commit suicide.²⁹ Many women die following a beating by their own husbands, and in most cases, the husband's free afterwards. The husband's according to Ilori, who are taken to court, are not given an adequate sentence for having killed a person. He added that in case of sexual violation, it may precondition the women to case of widows, lose all the property.³⁰ Physical injuries can range from bruises, cuts and burns to broken bones, stab wounds, miscarriages (in women), and death. He further notes that victims experience depression and other psychological distress, eating disorders, and alcohol and substance abuse problems, and they are more likely than other people to contemplate or attempt suicide.³¹

(iii) Psychological Effects

The psychological intense fear that the violence will happen again is generated in the woman. Low self-esteem, guilt, shame and depression also result; like which feeling of being unjustly treated and helpless. There may be accompanied by feelings of hatred and the desire for revenge.³² Among victims who are still living with their perpetrators, high amount of stress, fear and anxiety are commonly reported. He added that depression is also common, as victims are made to feel guilty for 'provoking' the abuse and are frequently subjected to intense criticism. He concluded that 60% of victims meet the diagnostic criteria for depression, either during or after termination of the relationship and have a greatly increased risk of suicidality.³³

(iv) Financial Effects

Once a victim leaves their perpetrators, they can be stunned with the reality of the extent to which the abuse has taken away their autonomy. Due to economic abuse and isolation, the victims usually have their little money of their own and few people in whom they can rely when seeking for help. This has been shown to be one of the greatest obstacles facing victims of domestic violence, and strongest fact that can discourage them from leaving their perpetrators. He concluded that in addition to lacking financial resources, victims of domestic violence often lack specialized skills, education, gainful employment and also may have several children to support.³⁴

(v) Long-term Effects

Domestic violence can trigger many different responses in victims, all of which are very relevant for a professional working with a victim. This according to Fareo, major consequences of domestic violence victimization include Psychological/mental health issues and chronic physical health problems. He equally notes that a victim's overwhelming lack of resources can lead to homelessness and poverty.³⁵

Finally, most experts agreed that economic and cultural factors play an especially powerful role in contributing to and perpetuating repeated abuse of women. Because women, as a group, tend to have less power in society, they are more likely to be victims and are less able to end abuse once it begins. Traditional beliefs, customs, and laws restrict the roles women may play and limit their economic opportunities, contributing to their dependence on men. Some scholars assert that the process of socialization teaches boys and girls a belief system that devalues women especially unmarried women and creates a sense of female responsibility for the maintenance of the family. Women who believe that the end of a relationship or of a marriage represents a personal failure are less likely to leave abusive relationship.³⁶

The Role of the Church in Curbing Domestic Violence

The starting point for our response in curbing domestic violence must be the recognition that all violence against women and children is morally unjust. They are human beings created by God in His own Image, and as such they are not inferior to men. They are entitled to be treated with respect. This truth needs to be communicated to boys and girls at a young age. Boys need to be educated at about the fact that they are no superior to women. They need to be taught that women are in no way respected and treated with dignity. Young girls too need to know that they are not inferior to male counterparts. They must be taught to assert their equality to men and to report acts of aggression against them and their children. Reporting involves recognizing that domestic violence is not private offence but a criminal one. As such it must be reported to the police who must act to restrain the perpetrator and prevent future violence. It is advisable to also report the matter to the pastors and elders of the Church. Violence is perpetuated by silence. When reported it can be monitored and checked.³⁷

Men must be taught that Jesus is to be their example when it comes to the way they treat women and children. In view of the above where wives are loved as Christ loved the Church, there can be no scope for physical and psychological violence against them. When children are treated in the same way that Jesus treated them, there will be no child abuse, but only the same loving disciplines that metes out to us. He concluded that not only the government and institutions but also the Church of God must work hard to break the vicious cycle of domestic violence that breeds hatred and more violence. Loving and caring families will produce loving and caring members of society.

Church should organize special programmes and seminars designed for members who are Married; this will go a long way in inculcating the culture of love for one another in the family and ultimately would help in curbing abuses in Christian homes. For the Christian community to live an exemplary lifestyle, the family life has to be well cultivated and built upon Godly principles. Arguably most of what is now troubling the Christian community today is the inevitable result of a family foundation. Because marriage is an important covenant made before God, there must be a high value placed on marriage and family. Great attention must be paid to scripture and the way in the Lord directs those who are married to live in peace, one with the other. This being the case, how is it, then, that violence would ever be accepted or condoned by the Lord and the Church? In all instances, scriptures conveying God's design for the way in which men, women, and children are to live together.³⁸

The above writer equally notes that the Church in curbing domestic violence, should organize marriage seminars for single men (especially the youth). It is now a proven fact that some men go into marriage without actually knowing what it entails, such people feel they need to get married just as long as they have made enough money to sustain themselves and their families. They suddenly believe they need someone to share with, forgetting that marriage is an everlasting union. Marriage seminars does not just enrich the mind of the individual involved but also prepares him/her for the challenges that lies ahead. The journey is a long lasting one.

Finally, in curbing domestic violence within the church, the Church should as matter of fact assume a level of accountability to the victims of domestic violence in its community. The New Testament speaks of the church as *ekklesia*, an assembly, congregation, or community. The words speak of people in relationship rather than edifice or an organization. The Acts of Apostles and the epistles teach that there is one church in many places and that believers who meet together for edification in various places are part of a single body whose head is Christ. The church is the spiritual family of brothers and sisters whose personal and corporate identity is rooted and grounded in the love of Christ (Ephesians 3:17).

When the Church meets together as a family, the members, ministers, to one another through teaching, fellowship, sharing, prayer (Acts 2:42), mutual service and encouragement (Hebrew 10:23-25), exercise of spiritual gifts (Rom. 12; 1 Cor. 11:17-30), and giving of thanks and worship (Ephesians 5:19-21). Therefore, a Church must be aware that violence and abusive behaviour are not strangers to the families attending the local Church. Because a Church is a body, it must function as a unit and give respect to all members of the body even those with a small or silenced voice. In nutshell, the Church should rise-up to its responsibilities and it should be

understood that the Church-those worshipping the living God must also see that the Church as a role in the care of families wounded internally by domestic violence.

Conclusion

As clearly stated above, domestic violence is one of the social evils within the church and the society at large. Domestic violence be it direct or indirect is against the law of God and humanity in general hence, it dehumanizes the status of women. The number of cases of domestic violence against women in the church and the society as a whole is at an alarming rate than that of men. In Nigeria today, as many ladies are humiliated by their spouses, more men equally die on yearly basis in the hands of their wives, because some women poison their husband food, beat them up and even cut off their husband's genital while fast asleep.

This is a clear indication that domestic violence is not restricted to ladies alone. Both men and women are victims of sexual abuse and domestic violence. In the Church of God today, the truth of the matter is that domestic violence is an evil act that remains hidden and avoided by Church leaders and even clergy men. The assembly of God's people must clearly understand that the voices of the ministers of the gospel and Church leaders matters a lot in the lives of the victims of domestic violence as well as the perpetrators of this evil act. Christian leaders are urged to adhere to Christ directive in the Garden of Gethsemane that His disciples should not tarry, rather to watch and pray (Matt. 26, 38, 41). In a nutshell, Christian leaders are called upon to do the same to the victims of domestic violence. They must rise up to their responsibilities to condemn this social evil in the Church of God and the society at large and proffer solutions in which can be done through prayers in Christ.

Recommendations

The leadership of the Church should organize seminars and outreach programmes where clergy men as well as professional counsellors are invited to enlighten people especially on the need for curbing violence in the society for national integration. Pre-marital sex and that of unwanted pregnancy, are unethical so, Christian couples to desist from it since, it is against God's law. Children to be treated in the same way that Jesus treated them, in so doing, there will be no child abuse, but only the same loving disciples that God metes out to us. Education of the couples be encouraged not minding the misunderstanding created as a result of the violence in order to avert future occurrence. Peaceful and conducive environment is needed for children to avert instability leading to domestic violence. On a final note, women must be empowered from an early stage, taught how to stand against bad traditional practices that are inimical to the gospel and undermine their human rights.

Endnotes

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